

AR6 Working Group III

FAIR Principles Supplementary Material

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Compiled by Alaa Al Khourdajie

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Background

The Task Group on Data Support for Climate Change Assessments (TG-Data) provides guidance to the IPCC and the Data Distribution Centre (DDC) on curation, traceability, stability, availability and transparency of data and scenarios related to the reports of the IPCC. This document provides tailored processes and guidelines that aim to implement the recommendations of TG-Data with focus on WG III’s contribution to AR6. For AR6, priority in WG III is given to figures, tables and exhibits included in the Summary for Policymakers (SPM) and Technical Summary (TS). The curated figures, tables, exhibits are given a Digital Object Identifier (DOI).

This Supplementary Material file provides an overview of the data curation activities and processes as part of WG III contribution to TG-Data workstream.

Data Curation

Types of data for curation

- 1- **Input data** The source material for the assessment report.
- 2- **Intermediate data** The outcome of data processing and analysis performed as part of the assessment. This may or may not be worthy of being archived or might be subject to licensing restrictions.
- 3- **Final data** The data directly displayed on a figure, included in a table or used as a key numerical value in the report.

Input Data used by WGIII

There are three major input datasets used for the contribution of WGIII to AR6. For emissions data: Chapter 2 on Historical Emissions Trends and Drivers in WG III's report compiled synthetic historical emissions dataset largely based on the Emissions Database for Global Atmospheric Research (EDGAR) provided by the Joint Research Centre (JRC) at the European Commission¹. This dataset is curated on Zenodo². For energy and relevant emissions data: WG III had access to various databases by the International Energy Agency (IEA). Due to licensing restrictions WGIII is also unable to curate the input data provided by IEA. For scenarios data: This data was collected and compiled throughout the assessment cycled via the Scenarios Explorer hosted at the International Institute for Applied System Analysis (IIASA)³. This dataset is curated on Zenodo⁴.

Data Storage

In the case of WGIII data, the DDC node designated for data storage is MetadataWorks (<https://metadataworks.co.uk/>).

The link for the WG III's Data Catalogue hosted at MetadataWorks is: <https://ipcc-browser.ipcc-data.org/browser/search?searchterm=working%20group%20iii>

¹ <https://edgar.jrc.ec.europa.eu/>

² Minx et al, 2022. A comprehensive and synthetic dataset for global, regional and national greenhouse gas emissions by sector 1970-2018 with an extension to 2019. <https://zenodo.org/record/6483002#.YmfPNNrMJD8>

³ AR6 Scenarios Explorer hosted at IIASA: <https://data.ene.iiasa.ac.at/ar6>

⁴ Byers et al, 2022. AR6 Scenarios Database. <https://zenodo.org/record/5886912#.YmfPFtrMJD8>

Process of data curation

This step-by-step process applies to all figures, exhibits and tables included in the SPM and TS of WGIII’s contribution to AR6.

The following steps were required for each figure:

- 1- A clean csv/excel copy of the final figure dataset. This file has to be formatted in the standard “tidy” data format.
- 2- Structural metadata file: This file contains an explanation of each Excel file or sheet, and variables. The following Structural Metadata Template was used.

Data Class	Data Class Description	Data Element	Data Element Description	Data Type	Measurement Unit
<i>Note: Can be based on the panel and/or data file name</i>	<i>Note: Description of the data class field</i>	<i>Note: this is the variable name in the data file</i>	<i>Note: this is the description of the variable name in the data file</i>	<p><i>Required.</i></p> <p><i>String (or str or text). Used for a combination of any characters that appear on a keyboard, such as letters, numbers and symbols.</i></p> <p><i>Character (or char). Used for single letters.</i></p> <p><i>Integer (or int). Used for whole numbers.</i></p> <p><i>Float (or Real). Used for numbers that contain decimal points, or for fractions.</i></p>	<i>Not Required if not applicable.</i>

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				<i>Boolean (or bool). Used where data is restricted to True/False or yes/no options.</i>	
<i>Input 1</i>	<i>Input 2...</i>				

3- A Data Archiving form: The form aims to provide fully traceability of the data sources and any processing undertaken to compute the final data appearing on a figure.

Report	WG III SPM
Figure Number and name (e.g. SPM.1)	
Authors Names	
List of all input research papers and grey literature sources Please provide links or DOIs where applicable. This step is crucial for traceability.	
Data Source If the data is provided by IEA (International Energy Agency) then we will use the follow statement → <i>OR</i> EDGAR (Emission Database for Global Atmospheric research) then we will use the following statement: →	<i>Based on data from IEA (20xx), CO2 Emissions from Fuel Combustion. All rights reserved; as modified by IPCC.</i> <i>OR</i> <i>Emissions data based on data from EDGAR (2021), EDGARv6 release. All rights reserved. Also published as: Minx, J. C.W. F. Lamb. M. Andrew. G. Canadell. Crippa. Döbbling... H. Tian, 2021: A comprehensive and</i>

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	<p><i>synthetic dataset for global, regional, and national greenhouse gas emissions by sector 1970–2018 with an extension to 2019. Earth Syst. Sci. Data, 13, 5213–5252, 38 doi:10.5194/essd-13-5213-2021.</i></p>
<p>Data processing or treatment</p> <p>Please provide a text based description of any data pre-processing or transformations undertaken to the input or source data in order to produce the figure in the report.</p> <p>This is important if the traceable dataset or numbers are different from those appearing on the figure. The reader should be able to understand how we arrived to the final data appearing on the SPM figure from reading this field, and should be able to replicate the steps. Therefore, the level of details presented here should be enabling such replication.</p>	

GitHub Repository

WG III’s TSU is planning to host a GitHub repository (<https://github.com/IPCC-WG3>) through which all final data files will be shared. This is not to replace the MetadataWorks Data Catalogue, but to provide an additional medium for sharing the data.

Citation

The input data should additionally be cited in the report by including data citations in the body or figure captions of the AR6 with a corresponding reference in the reference list. The citations for the datasets and code should be inserted using the reference management software used for the preparation of the report (e.g. Mendeley). This information will be published as a pop-up box on the web-based report alongside figures with their DOIs.

Referencing for IEA's Data

Authors should give full acknowledgement to the IEA as being the source of any IEA Data, and Derived Data, that is reproduced in or in relation to WG III AR6. Below are IEA requirement.

Sourcing notices for the *databases* are:

- a notice to confirm whenever IPCC has modified IEA Data, such notice to appear alongside any Derived Data howsoever presented in the caption of the figure as well as in the metadata.

e.g. Based on data from IEA (2018), CO2 Emissions from Fuel Combustion, <https://webstore.iea.org/co2-emissions-from-fuel-combustion-2018>. As modified by IPCC.

Sourcing notices for the *datasets* are:

- a notice to confirm whenever IPCC has modified IEA Further Data, such notice to appear alongside any Derived Data based on the IEA Further Data howsoever presented in the caption of the figure as well as in the metadata.

Based on data from IEA (20XX). As modified by IPCC.